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DEVELOPING NEW METHODS AND TOOLS
FOR THE INTEGRATED SUSTAINABILITY
ASSESSMENT OF WATER.
The MATISSE Project and
the Ebro River Basin.

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Methods and Tools for
Integrated Sustainability Assessment

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MATISSE (Methods and Tools for Integrated Sustainability Assessment) aims to achieve a step-wise advance in the science and application of Integrated Sustainability Assessment (ISA) of EU policies. In order to reach this objective the core activity of the MATISSE project is to improve the tools available for conducting Integrated Sustainability Assessments.

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The MATISSE Working Papers can be downloaded at <http://www.matisse-project.net/>.

Preface

About the MATISSE project

The MATISSE (Methods and Tools for Integrated Sustainability Assessment) project is funded by the European Commission, DG Research, within the 6th Framework Programme. The project is interested in the role that Integrated Sustainability Assessment (ISA) could play in the process of developing and implementing policies capable of addressing persistent problems of unsustainable development and supporting transitions to a more sustainable future in Europe. The core activity of MATISSE is to develop, test and demonstrate new and improved methods and tools for conducting ISA.

This work is carried out through developing and applying a conceptual framework for ISA, looking at the linkages to other sustainability assessment processes, linking existing tools to make them more useable for ISA, developing new tools to address transitions to sustainable development and applying the new and improved tools within an ISA process through a series of case studies.

The extent to which the case studies are carrying out a complete ISA for their area of focus varies between attempts to cover all phases of an ISA process to partial implementation of the process. Equally, different case studies are oriented to developing and testing tools and approaches to some, but not all, of the methodological challenges of ISA. The case studies are complementary, however, and the set of cases offers the opportunity to address a wide range of methodological challenges and to explore linkages between cases. An evaluation of practical experiences with ISA implementation in the case studies will provide guidance on the further improvement of methods and tools. Results will also contribute to more informed policy advice.

What is ISA?

Within the MATISSE project, Integrated Sustainability Assessment (ISA) has been defined as a cyclical, participatory process of scoping, envisioning, experimenting, and learning through which a shared interpretation of sustainability for a specific context is developed and applied in an integrated manner, in order to explore solutions to persistent problems of unsustainable development. ISA is conceptualised as a complement to other forms of sustainability assessment, such as Sustainability Impact Assessment, Integrated Assessment and Regulatory Impact Assessment. Whereas these other forms of assessment fulfil the pragmatic need for *ex ante* screening of incremental sectoral policies that are developed within the prevailing policy regime, ISA is conceptualised as a support to longer-term and more strategic policy processes, where the objective is to explore persistent problems of unsustainable development that have a systemic pathology and possible solutions to these. ISA is therefore oriented toward supporting the development of cross-sectoral policies that specifically address sustainable development and at exploring enabling policy regimes and institutional arrangements.

MATISSE Working Papers

Matisse Working Papers are interim reports of project activities that are published in order to illustrate ongoing work and some provisional conclusions, as well as providing the opportunity for discussion of the approaches taken by the project and interim results. This discussion should be both within the project and between project members and the broader scientific and policy communities. Readers are encouraged to contact the authors to discuss the content of MATISSE Working Papers.

Jill Jäger and Paul Weaver
Editors of the MATISSE Working Paper Series

Abstract

Persistent unsustainable problems are not problems occurring ‘out there’, independently from our individual and collective behaviours in our daily interactions with the environment. Most current methods and tools for the assessment and management of unsustainability tend to focus on representing apparently-distant biophysical changes, rather than deepening the understanding of personal and agents’ behaviours, motives and values. They therefore tend to show unsustainability problems as problems of “others”. In practice, existing assessment methods and tools tend to limit their scope of assessment to one single area of reality, deal only with one type of knowledge and, often, are addressed to the wrong communities of action and change. The EU MATISSE project aims at developing new reflective methods and tools capable of overcoming some of these pitfalls by supporting the co-production of socially and ecologically robust, and systemic narratives and visions that may stimulate transition learning and action on persistent unsustainability problems. Such narratives and visions, we argue, can be better developed, within the context of the new approach of *Integrated Sustainability Assessment* (ISA), if they take relational agent-based perspective.

Our paper provides a first description of an application of ISA to river basin management within the context of the EU project MATISSE. The paper reports on the application of the first stages of the ISA process framework (scoping and visioning) using participatory approaches in a case-study of the Ebro river basin. First results show that an emerging vision of sustainability entails a great deal of collaboration between agents working at different levels, as opposed to a fragmented world in which actors pursue their interests and benefits in an un-coordinated, exploitative and short-sighted manner. In their vision, stakeholders underline how multi-scale, multi-domain and multi-time problems such as the relationships between upstream/downstream, global/local, and short-term/long-term socio-economic processes need to be incorporated into the assessment and policy processes aimed at enhancing the *socioecological resilience* and sustainability of complex water systems such as the Ebro river basin.

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Developing new methods and tools for the Integrated Sustainability Assessment of water. The MATISSE project and the Ebro River Basin.

1. Introduction

Persistent unsustainability problems are not problems that occur ‘out there’, independently from our individual, collective and daily multi-scale behaviours and interactions with the environment. Unsustainability is the cumulative result of the reproduction of a structural set of relations between natural and social systems that create a mounting number of unintended, negative and irreversible consequences both for humans and natural systems. In policy, persistent problems of unsustainability can be understood as those generated by the reiterative adoption of wrong solutions (usually of a non-systemic and short-term guise) to daily collective problems.

Most current tools for the assessment and management of environmental problems tend to focus on one area of reality, or be based solely in one type of knowledge, and in this way they tend to suffer from a great deal of reductionism. The situation highlights the need for new approaches at the science-policy-society interfaces to deal with such problems and to facilitate transition paths to more sustainable system futures. A more systemic and integrative view both in science and policy is essential. In this paper we focus on exploring the possibilities for building a assessment methodology with in contrast to the existing procedures, such as Impact Assessment or Strategic Environmental Assessment has the following characteristics: 1. it is transition oriented, rather than simply incremental and at building on existing regime, 2. it aims a reframing, social learning and empowering stakeholders 3. follows a multi-level, agent based approach. 4. It’s mostly anticipatory, being concerned with ex-ante assessment, 5. Departs from a precautionary stance in which impacts are largely unknown, 6. And takes an holistic and cyclical approach. 7. Assesses multiple trade-offs between option and attempts to create pathways synergetic of policy action and social change to overcome these. This methodology has received the label of *Integrated Sustainability Assessment* (Weaver et al. 2005).

The EU project MATISSE (Methods and Tools for the Integrated Sustainability Assessment, 2005-2008) is a three year EU project aimed at developing basic research in the area of sustainability science, transition theory and Integrated Assessment. Its objective is to develop and improve the methods, procedures and tools for the Integrated Assessment of persistent problems, such as the unsustainable use of water resources. MATISSE sets out to develop new methods and tools capable of supporting the creation of new relational and systemic narratives that can incorporate stakeholders’ visions of more attractive and sustainable futures. For MATISSE, the primary objects of assessment are socio-ecologic systems under a range of dynamic driving forces, including the influence of prospective policies, programmes and action plans. Under this framework, MATISSE has defined Integrated Sustainability Assessment (ISA) as *a cyclical, participatory process of scoping, envisioning, experimenting, and learning through which a shared interpretation of sustainability for a specific context is developed and applied in an integrated manner in order to explore solutions to persistent problems of unsustainable development* (Weaver et al. 2005).

The aim of this paper is to introduce this conceptual framework and the defining characteristics of ISA and to illustrate their application in the MATISSE work package on water. Our illustration concerns one of the participatory *Integrated Assessment focus groups* (IA-FGs, Kasemir, et al. 2003) being held in the Ebro Delta to frame and help build understanding about the nature of persistent problems of unsustainable development in the river basin, to envision shared sustainable futures, and analyse the feasibility of the ISA in a particular social context representative of

processes and conflicts around the use of water occurring elsewhere. Certainly, water constitutes a very special domain to express the type of unsustainable relationships humans systems maintain with natural systems, as well as of the type of multi-scale policy assessments that need to be made when dealing with a fundamental and (on a global scale) an increasingly scarce natural resource (Gleick, 2003). This notwithstanding, the case of water illustrates how sustainability problems not only stem from ‘natural’ scarcity situations but are relational and hybrid results of the prevalence of conflicting cultural worldviews on the meaning of natural resources, their role in society, and on the relationships between natural and social systems in general (Tàbara 2006, 2005).

2. The MATISSE project: developing the ISA framework

The lack of systemic analytical methods and tools able to handle tackle persistent problems of unsustainable development capable to integrate social, institutional and cultural dimensions provides the basis of the MATISSE project. Most expert knowledge (scientific and technical) addresses environmental changes mainly by focussing on their final and separate effects – reductive, fragmented approaches- rather than dealing with the whole network of relationships between their ultimate causes and their systemic effects on the global socioecologic system. The MATISSE project is not only concerned with improving understanding of the systemic implications of the continuously-evolving concept of ‘sustainable development’, but also with exploring the basis for an operational integration of sustainability into policy processes and structures. In this sense, the MATISSE project to a certain extent adopts a perspective akin, albeit critical, to the current discussions on ‘mode-II’ science insofar as it aims at providing useful knowledge in its context of application, hence socially distributed and socially robust knowledge which stems from a close communication with stakeholders (Muller 2003, Gibbons et al. 1994, Nowotny et al. 2001). We understand that sustainability knowledge must aim at meeting the criterion of ‘strong contextualisation’, although, at the same time, must be able to inform and integrate the knowledge and lessons learnt from external sources and other contexts and domains.

Participatory *Integrated Sustainability Assessment* (ISA) tries to go beyond the existing procedures of Environmental Impact Assessment or Strategic Environmental Assessment. In particular, ISA is about searching for and applying a paradigm-change for regime change, rather than using in an incremental way the existing policy and science paradigms to reinforce, or legitimate, current regime practices. In its participatory guise, the making of policy options in ISA is not considered only as a result of an expert knowledge process, hence neglecting other types of knowledge, worldviews, perceptions and values. More importantly, ISA is understood as a mutual learning experience, which arises from direct interactions with non-expert social agents in the definition of problems and options as well as the methods and tools to assess them. The use of knowledge only from the natural sciences is recognised as insufficient to fully grasp the complexities of unsustainability, and in this sense, social sciences and participatory methods can play a crucial role in improving the relevance of the defined policy options and their implementation.

MATISSE purpose is to generate methods and tools based on these integrative, systemic, multi-scale, and co-evolutionary perspectives. It aims at relating them to mid- and long-term policy questions, such as what kinds of socioeconomic development futures and what pathways of change might be feasible and compatible with these futures, and how normative concerns for sustainability might be integrated into policy making processes. The framework of ISA, which is closely related to the ideas of transition theory as developed by Jan Rotmans and his collaborators is shown in Figure 1.¹

¹ For more details on ISA process see Weaver and Rotmans (2006) and Van der Brugge, et al. (2005).

Figure 1 - ISA within MATISSE

- **The Scoping stage:** It aims at exploring in a participatory and qualitative way the definition of the unsustainability persistent problems of the system of reference, the main forcers driving such change and the different perceptions and definitions about them. It should be based on an accurate integrated system analysis at different scales and an a careful identification and identification of stakeholders capable to provide a socially and ecologically robust description of the context in which the ISA is to be applied.
- **Envisioning stage:** It is aimed at the development of visions of sustainable futures in the context of application of the PAF by providing a common interpretation of sustainability. The ‘problems’ of unsustainability need to be transformed into challenges for action and specified in an empowering and engaging narrative. Scenario can be designed and the different pathways to attain to the different future need to be evaluated according to their social-ecological effects. This phase involves the formulation of policy options in close interaction with stakeholders implicitly or explicitly considered in the scenarios.
- **Experimenting stage:** During this phase, a series testing and reflection activities are carried out by the systematic use of specific tools which allow participants to experience situations and alternatives of action that otherwise could not be able to experience unless under carried out controlled or simulated conditions. This may include the use of modelling, role gaming, and/and field experiments. In this stage, a series of ISA oriented experiments are selected, designed and evaluated on the basis of the previous two stages and sustainability visions and policy proposals are tested in terms of consistency, adequacy, robustness and feasibility. The impacts and the trade-offs for each transition pathway (scenarios) are explored.
- **Evaluation and learning:** Finally, social learning is assessed both on content (e.g. what specific policy proposals) as of process (what tools and methods worked or not). The evaluation stages should provide inputs for the project team to adjust processes, tools, methods and assumptions in the next round. This stage include an evaluation of the stakeholder interaction as of the monitoring of the different stages, of the process and it is understood that a ISA process includes at least a full iteration of each of these four stages.

Now we move to show an illustration of how this procedural template is being used in the Ebro River Basin. The present paper only shows part of a larger on-going work carried out during the first year of the project (on scoping and envisioning) and we only focus on the description and analysis of one of the several meetings with stakeholders that are being held in that context. In particular, this illustration concentrates in the second of the meetings with stakeholders and places an special attention on the river basin delta.

3. ISA application in the Ebro Delta

3.1. The context

Deltas are social-ecological systems with an increasing vulnerability to accelerating global environmental change. First, they increasingly experience the impact of human activities, mostly due to patterns of human occupation and exploitation combined with a mounting number of economic, social, and recreational activities inland. Secondly, climate change and accelerated sea level rise threaten lowlands, which in many cases is a situation aggravated by subsidence phenomena as a result of aquifer overexploitation (IPCC 2001). Traditional management strategies based on a partial, reductionist view of the problems regarding the use and management of water resources in these environments have often proved inefficient to deal with them and have provoked the emergence of other sources of water unsustainability. To a large extent, a delta can be seen as a *microcosm* and a socioecological *meta-indicator*, indicative of a whole array of unsustainable processes occurring within the river basin system and beyond. This is very much the case in the Ebro delta.

Pictures 1 & 2 - Ebro River Basin location and aerial view of its Delta.

The Ebro River Basin is located in the north-eastern part of the Iberian peninsula (picture 2). It is the largest hydrological basin of Spain and flows into a delta that represents one of the most interesting wetland areas in the Mediterranean basin with its rich biodiversity. The 330 km² of surface are characterized by a flat landscape, low population (15.000 inhabitants) and a high ecological value in terms of containing several designated Ramsar sites important for bird migration and the presence of rare plants, fish and invertebrates. However, and despite the apparent wilderness, the Delta is strongly shaped by human activities. The present form is the result of more than two centuries of human intervention. Several socioeconomic activities, mainly within the primary sector (e.g. agriculture, fishing, aquaculture and hunting) have shaped its current landscape. Among the current land uses in the Ebro Delta, the rice crop is particularly relevant as it occupies around 65% of the total delta's surface. In addition, tourism has become more significant in recent years. Urbanisation in the Delta is not very intense. Apart from several farm houses, only two towns (Deltebre and Sant Jaume) concentrate urban uses in the area. However, the urbanization pressure, mostly as second house residence, is becoming widespread and represents an increasing threat to the conservation of the Delta natural heritage in the near future (pictures 3-6).

*Pictures 3-5. Some environmental pressures of the Ebro River basin:
Nuclear power stations, chemical industry and
urbanisation pressures in the Ebro Delta.*

One of the most outstanding symptoms of persistent unsustainability of the Ebro river basin system –as well as in other Spanish river basins- was expressed in the conflicts that arose from the making of and failed attempt to implement the last National Water Plan (NWP). This Plan, which was withdrawn by the new left-wing government after the national elections in 2004, proposed a water transfer from the Ebro river basin to other ‘deficit’ river basins. The proposal was highly criticised for not taking the social and ecological impacts of the whole Ebro river basin sufficiently into account, and because it framed the issue merely as a ‘water scarcity problem’ (that is, simply as an economic demand/supply optimisation question) rather than considering multiple issues of river basin resource and landscape management in a more systemic and comprehensive way. The National Hydrological Plan caused a wide social upheaval, manifested in the largest demonstrations on socio-environmental issues taking place in Spain for over two decades. This resulted in the creation of new collaborative networks of action, even with previously conflicting groups, which engaged most of the relevant social actors within the Ebro river basin. A wide range of stakeholders, who were working independently on their own individual activities, started building a new cross-cutting social movement, which was named the ‘New Water Culture’. This conflict exemplifies how an external pressure that threatens the whole system in which even conflicting agents operate, may be the trigger for a social re-organisation that leads to the creation of new institutions to cope with that threat². Among the self-defined goals of this social movement, the aim has been to move from a traditional management model based on water supply to water demand management (FNCA 2005).

² It is worth noting that such threats which operate as triggers of transition are not simply a biophysical threat, but mostly an institutional one, or more specifically a biophysical threat mediated by social institutions (in this case political institutions). Hence, more research is needed to understand what type of triggers, and in what conditions, sustainability transitions start in the first place (see Tàbara & Ilhan, 2006).

3.2. Integrated Sustainability Assessment focus groups

Rather than carry out an extensive literature review of participatory approaches to science and policy making, we focus our attention here on our experience in one of the exercises carried out in the context of the application of ISA in the domain of water³. Our approach is based on previous experience in the development of a methodology called *Integrated Assessment focus groups* (IA-FGs) for which the specific procedure and origins can be found in Kasemir, et al. (2003) and Dürrenberger, et al. (1999) and for the case of water management in Hare et al. (2006).

As mentioned above, the ISA approach consists of four main stages (scoping, envisioning, experimenting and learning). In the following we describe, a participatory process that was carried in the selected study area of the Ebro Delta, as part of series of IA-FGs that are taking place in the river basin and focus mostly in the first two stages of the ISA. We describe here the second of our meetings with stakeholders, which was held in Tortosa, 10 March, 2006. The participants were recruited from representative institutions that play an active role in the Ebro Delta management (New Water Foundation Culture, Birdlife-Spain (environmental NGO), Catalan Water Agency, Regional Council of Ebro Delta, Municipality, Farmers, and the Ebro Delta Natural Park.

One of the main purposes of the meeting was to observe whether the ISA process could encourage the emergence and integration of different types of knowledge, and to learn how the approach could be implemented in practice, including what type of tools, such as computer models, could be necessary or useful to support these processes. Ours was a deliberative exercise to obtain insights on how the stakeholders perceive and interpret the persistent problems of the Delta, how they saw the relationships among different dimensions of the problems at scale and the scales of possible action within the river basin. Hence, we aimed at finding out more about:

The stakeholders' perceptions and interpretations of the problems of unsustainability that persist in the Ebro Delta, in particular, identifying the driving forces (causes-effects-responses) that decrease the sustainability of the area.

The public's perspective on future scenarios for the Ebro Delta in 30 years, through which it is possible to elucidate strategies or pathways that help to reach the future states.

In order to reach both objectives, a series of participatory exercises was organised, intended to cover the stages of scoping and visioning in a sequential mode. The first one was articulated around a cause-effect-response matrix divided into the different dimensions (ecological, economic, social, institutional, cultural, technological, others). The aim was to discuss and deliberate around a *shared vision of unsustainability problems* in the Ebro Delta. The second consisted of a visioning exercise using the collage technique (Kasemir 2000; pictures 7 & 8) to create a *sustainable* scenario of the Delta in contrast to a *business as usual* one. For that exercise the participants were split into two small groups and each of them was asked to support the creation of scenarios making 'collages' on land-use maps of the Delta.

³ For an illustration of different but related approaches see Sarwer-Foner, B. Participatory Action Research, An Annotated Bibliography. Available at: http://www.ssmu.mcgill.ca/qpirg/gradfiles/par_annotated_biblio.pdf; also see R. Chambers (2005). However, it is important to note that ISA is mostly aimed a institutional regime change, not only working at empowering stakeholders at community level.

3.3. Results of the scoping stage: ‘Welcome to the Delta’s complexity’⁴

As a result of the first participatory exercise, a system representation of the baseline problems in the Ebro Delta was drawn by the stakeholders, the results of which are shown in table 1. Simply, stakeholders were asked to discuss and fill freely the table with their first ideas, as a way to start the discussion.

At the beginning, the main focus of attention was related to problems directly linked with the environmental dimension (e.g. pollution, subsidence, deforestation, ...), which were understood to be the result of the past and present practices in the exploitation and management of the natural resources of the river basin, under what has been called the ‘structuralism paradigm’. But progressively and in contrast, a more systemic and relational worldview emerged during the discussions. Several participants perceived and explained the Delta’s changes and its evolution as a close, dynamic relationship between natural resources and their exploitation: ‘Changes in rice crop production affect biodiversity’; ‘water irrigation management affects crops...’ So it appeared among the participants that a more complex and richer perspective was needed to comprehend the system. As it was expected, the economic dimension was perceived as a significant driving force of change. The increasing tourist pressures and the crisis of the agricultural sector were underlined as the main ones.

However, as the activity proceeded, the focus shifted to the institutional context. One of the most relevant results of the workshop was the strong perception the participants developed about the key role of the institutional dimension when thinking about the sustainability of the Ebro Delta. The participants agreed on the lack of integrated management of the river basin due to an institutional fragmentation. For example, they mentioned the impacts caused downstream due to construction of dams. Water regulation for irrigation, industrial and urban uses, and flood risk control have provoked regression and subsidence problems in the delta system. This is seen as the result of a sectoral management of the river and a partial problem framing by conventional assessment methods. Another example given was the historical division of the Delta into two administratively separate parts, which often do not collaborate with each other. The northern and southern hemideltas belong to different administrative counties (*comarques*).

⁴ As said by one of our participants.

	ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	INSTITUTIONAL	CULTURAL	TECHNOLOGIC
C A U S E S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural market sustainability • River Basin Regulations • Tourism • Lack of Economic Resources at local level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intensive agriculture • Deforestation • Wind engery parks • Foreign species introduction • Ecosystems fragility • Landscapel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of integrated management • Public Participation • Urban Laws disconnected with landscapel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional Power structures • No individual conscience • No Universitys in the region • Old water Culture • No participation • Humaniz action process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydroelectric Powertrains • Uncontrolled groundwater
E F F E C T S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rice production dereasing • New project, now social conflicts • Human occuation of risky spaces close to the river 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salinization • Subsidence • Habitat loss Contamination • Species lossDisadvateges to the primary sector • Delta regression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non coordinated administions 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River flow stabilization • Breaking dynamics of water systems
R E S P O N S E S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality Labeling for local Farm product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard protective measures • Water quality • Water circulation • Environmental indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associations • Institutional coordination • Agenda 21 • Non normative management plans • Cooperation plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socioal movements 	

Table 1 - Cause-effect-response matrix used by the participants during the workshop

The general perception of the participants was that there are too many overlapping administrative bodies responsible for different parts of River Basin Management, although most importantly that a much stronger coordination between them is needed, especially when they are from different institutional levels (national, central or local). For instance, in the coastal areas, the Public Maritime Domain is in the hands of the Central Spanish Government (Directorate of Coasts within Ministry of Environment), whereas the inner coastal zone, like the Natural Park, is under the control of the Catalan autonomous government and the management of the navigation channels is the responsibility of the Spanish Ministry of Public Works . And at the same time, many other competences relate to the land management and regulating economic activities in the area belong to

counties, provincial and municipal administration. Precisely this was seen as a many hindrance to overcome current unsustainable trends.

Thus, one of the questions that arose from this exercise was the following: what design for the institutional context would permit people to cope with unsustainable problems in a more collaborative way?

3.4. Results of the envisioning stage: two contrasting perspectives on the future

The two pairs of scenarios –two per subgroup- were quite different, although they can be grouped in two categories. After a plenary session the participants named and described them as follows:

- **Technical-expert future:** These visions were mainly focussed on explaining the causes of the multiple problems as if it is was possible to deal with them one per one, on an individual basis. Such problems such as those derived from energy extraction, coastal erosion loss of aquaculture or population growth, may be dealt with technical and expert solutions. Generally, these proposals were believe also to improve and reinforce the biophysical capacity of the system to cope with environmental problems. And in this sense, despite being of a managerial style, several identified proposals were innovative and had a quite systemic perspective, like the ‘managed realignment strategy’ of the shoreline and the restoration of the wetlands in order to deal with changes and dynamics of the Delta (Ledoux 2004). In Spain, this kind of alternative has never been considered in a realistic option for coastal management.

- **Socio-institutional future:** These visions were related to the institutional and organisational aspects, so as to enhance the collaboration between agents working at different levels, as opposed to a fragmented world in which individuals and organisations pursue their interests and benefits in an un-coordinated, exploitative and short-sighted manner. One of the main findings of the workshop held with local stakeholders in the Ebro Delta was that there is an urgent need to coordinate and strengthen social networks to achieve sustainability. It seems clear that sustainability implies a large degree of empowerment and coordination between different agents at different scales. In particular, an emerging vision of sustainability is that unsustainability is the result of the lack of conscious collaboration between agents working at different levels with the overall goal to reduce their impacts on aquatic systems and on other agents. Although participants believe that beauty of the landscape and the ecological value of the Delta is the main sustainability resource, this depends on the better organisation, planning and coordination of the institutional context.

Pictures 7 & 8 - Envisioning exercise using the collage technique (Kasemir et al. 2000)

3.5. Discussion

ISA aims at appraising unsustainable persistent problems from a systemic and multi-scale perspective and therefore is based on the acknowledgement of the need to integrate social diversity and plural patterns of interpretation of the system under study. In this sense, ISA can be understood as a tool for the larger societal process of *sustainability learning* (Tàbara 2005). In our participatory exercise, the application of the two first stages of the ISA helped in promoting the integration of different kinds of knowledge in the evaluation process and tried to approach our discourse in a multi-scale, participatory, and systemic fashion. For that purpose, within the MATISSE work package on water we are also developing a multi-scale, social agent-based model called the World Cellular model, in which stakeholders also participate in the initial stages of its development (Tàbara et al. 2006).

Specifically, the scoping exercise contributed to an in-depth representation of drivers of unsustainability within the Ebro Delta. It was possible to assess relationships between the origins and the effects of processes of both human and natural systems dynamics in an interrelated and integrated way. Through the cause-effect-matrix exercise the participants were able to connect the impacts of human actions with economic, cultural, ecological, technological and institutional dimensions. But at the same time, many processes could not find an easy classification in that probably too rigid, over-framed and separate classification of problem categories, effects and responses. However, the activity helped to uncover some linkages among multi-scale processes in water management in their different spatial scales of action – local, meso, and global, and from the very individual to the global. Another output of this exercise was the emergence of systemic and relational worldviews. The perception of the Delta as a dynamic area and as a result of bi-directional relationships between nature and society confirmed the presence of a co-evolutionary worldviews among the stakeholders. This contrasted with the hegemonic discourse of the traditional hydraulic paradigm of increasing water supply and defending ‘nature control by society’. In that sense, the scoping phase opened up the debate and broadened the problem framing.

In the envisioning exercises our expectations were that the process would promote the integration of those worldviews that drive the Ebro river basin towards the shared sustainable vision. Through the participative procedure some emerging perspectives and perceptions increasingly highlighted the need to address institutional issues in order to enhance future sustainability of the Delta. These were in contrast with conventional perspectives characteristic of more traditional assessment processes that are focused on end-of-pipe and separate *effects* -once they have already entered into the socio-ecologic systems and are dealt with in a fragmented way- rather than dealing with *the whole network of relationships between the ultimate causes and their systemic effects* on the social-ecological systems. The former perspective was referred to as *socio-institutional* while the latter was called *technical-expert*. However, it is likely that these perspectives are not exclusive but complementary and a real effort should be made to integrate them as part of the whole assessment process.

The importance of the institutional context and of building social capital to cope with external perturbations was acknowledged in the *socio-institutional future*. This finding is not new and has been discussed extensively in the existing literature. As argued by several authors (Adger, 2005; Berkes et al. 2002; Folke et al. 2002; Olson, 2004), the existence and creation of new institutions and collaborative networks of action and social capital can be of crucial importance to provide resilience to social ecological systems. Social capital can provide better means to cope with abrupt changes and hence improve the resilience of local populations, particularly in the context of resource-dependent livelihoods, as is the case in some traditional economic sectors of the Ebro Delta. Also, as stated by Olson (2004) adaptive capacities are needed to deal with environmental perturbations. Collective action is also recognised by Adger (2003) as one strategy to increase adaptive capacities of social-ecological systems to face future uncertainties, especially those

coming from climatic changes. The conflict, which arose from the threat posed by the National Hydrological Plan (NHP), indeed catalysed the building of social capital and networks of trust among actors who not only were unused to collaboration, but who have even looked at each other as enemies. In the Ebro river basin the threat motivated a response that led to the emergence of a new and strong communal identity. Many participative institutions and new forums of discussion were created, although the challenge now seems to be how to organize these. Our stakeholders are aware that more coordination among these institutions is needed.

In short, participants believed that more coordinated collective action is necessary to prevent the unsustainable problems and to adapt to the changing future and dynamic environment that characterise the Delta. But this may depend on building trust and social capital in the first place. To a large extent, *the problems of unsustainability* –and the possible development of pathways to deal with them- *are problems of identity and responsibility* –of understanding that such problems are not just ‘out there’ and have nothing to do with our personal actions, values and behaviours. In this sense, it now becomes clearer that methods and tools of ISA that support collective action in a bottom-up participatory fashion and take into account such relational approaches are well suited to reach this goal. This may result in assessment and management practices less based on delegation and more based on personal engagement. The question then arises in our case about how much it can be possible to contribute to this cooperation and organisation of the large number of formal and informal social networks that sprang from the debunking of the NHP, once the ‘threat’ of such a plan has to some extent passed. Our exercise has helped in reflecting on the opportunities and difficulties for transitional changes towards sustainability and in particular about the great challenge of how ‘to learn to collaborate’.

4. Conclusion

One of the main insights that we obtained from applying the ISA process in the context of the Ebro Delta was a vision from stakeholders of *sustainability as a situation in which relevant agents continuously learn to collaborate for the common good*. This does not mean that all actors have the same set of goals and interests that drive their actions, nor that all of them share the same worldviews and ideas about the future. Rather, it means that the different views of the future are not necessarily completely at odds with each other, and that a certain degree of complementary and of positive synergies can be found among them within a minimally common understanding of the problem situation (that is, about what the problem is, but not necessarily about what we need to do about it)⁵. Clearly, this is just one vision of sustainability, and still opposed to others, which may not even consider sustainability as a problem, and which are present and influence the management of natural resources. In our research a ‘socio-institutional’ vision of sustainability was contrasted with another one which appeared under the heading of the ‘technical-expert’ perspective, indicating that a move in the path of sustainability transition may need to integrate the two.

Hence, our results are only part of the scoping and visioning stage of a fully-fledged ISA process, still ongoing. ISA provides a structured framework that permits the integration of different sources of knowledge in the process of framing, envisioning and elucidating strategies, pathways and

⁵ Learning to accept and benefit from opposed points of view and perspectives occurs in many other fields of social development and organisation. For instance, in the quest to guarantee of religious rights or sexual tolerance, institutions may be devised for the common good of creating spaces for mutual understanding and respect (institutional tolerance accepts diverse perspectives but not intolerance). Likewise, institutions and social processes aimed at guaranteeing sustainability should be able to protect, be capable to gain from, and defend a diversity of legitimate or even opposite positions –also departing from a common understanding of the common situation and of the problems. Nevertheless, in some cases, it may be necessary to contest those positions which are completely against with the minimum socially accepted and scientifically validated standards of sustainability, although the large uncertainties in this field may better suggest to take a precautionary approach in all instances.

system interventions towards sustainability regime change. We have provided an example of an operationalisation of ISA in the specific context of the Ebro delta. Through the first stages of the ISA with stakeholders we have underlined how multi-scale, multi-domain and multi-time problems such as the relationships between upstream/downstream, global/local, and short-term/long-term socio-economic processes need to be incorporated into the assessment and policy processes aimed at enhancing the *socioecological resilience* and sustainability of complex water systems such as the Ebro river basin. This impinges directly on the issues of power and peoples' responsibilities, which most current methods and tools for the assessment of water resources often overlook. In other words, to a large extent, assessing sustainability in this fashion shifts the emphasis of the discussion from 'what is the problem' towards assessing *who is responsible*. In that way, we need to create new methods and tools able to unveil who has most of the burden of the causes of unsustainability as well as most of the capacity to participate in the making and implementation of possible pathways of action to deal with them. In particular, new, new criteria and processes for multi-agent collaboration, built on extended identities of interest, need to be developed within the context of an greater awareness of the consequences of each social agent's action and their impact on other agents. New methods and tools may be necessary, but these will be useful only if they really contribute to substantially transform current system relationships.

However, many difficulties remain. One of the criteria of quality in Integrated Sustainability Assessment should be closeness and relevance to decision-making. At present, we have only conceived our process as an exercise to learn how ISA should be, rather than to show how ISA is, e.g. as a tool to guide transitional policy processes and decisions in concrete situations. In our case, the ISA was still performed as a basic research experiment and our expectations regarding its influence for decision-making processes were still necessarily low. But on the other hand, the analysis of the visions of sustainability through the integration of different sources of knowledge has broadened our understanding and has enormously enriched our assessment of the whole system dynamics and the kind of problems that we confront in the domain of the sustainable management of water resources.

In particular, our application of ISA for the case of water allowed us to better identify those key elements which drive current unsustainability, not only from our 'expert' perspective but more importantly from the perspective of the 'people of the context'. Hence, deliberative processes might open up new debates and improve the capacities for greater awareness and control over negative consequences of different policy alternatives and measures. Our procedure, hopefully, has led to the identification of an array of more socially and ecologically robust policy options; and some of them may be more adaptive with regard to the fast-changing system dynamics occurring now in the area. Nevertheless, further research is needed to understand and assess to what extent these options can be translated into the policy process as to contribute to enhancing socioecological resilience and adaptive capacity both from the biophysical side (e.g. wetland restoration through managed realignment) and from the socio-cultural side (e.g. institutional coordination and collaboration). This has been considered in the experimenting and evaluating phase of the ISA process.

References

- Adger, N. W., T. P. Hughes C. Folke Stephen R. Carpenter, J. Rockström. (2005). Social-Ecological Resilience to Coastal Disasters. *Science*: 1036-1039.
- Adger, N. A. (2003). Social Capital, Collective Action, and Adaptation to Climate Change. *Economic Geography* 79:387-404.
- Berkes, F. and D. Jolly (2002). Adapting to climate change: Social-ecological resilience in a Canadian Western Arctic community. *Conservation Ecology* 5.
- Chambers, R. (2005). *Ideas for Development*. London: Earthscan.
- Dürrenberger, G., J. Behringer, U. Dahinden, A. Gerger, B. Kasemir, C. Querol, R. Schüle, D. Tàbara, F. Toth, M. Van Asselt, D. Vassilarou, N. Willi, C. C. Jaeger (1999). *Focus Groups in Integrated Assessment. A Manual for a Participatory Tool*. Ulysses Working Paper WP-97-2. Darmstadt University of Technology.
- Folke, C., S. Carpenter, T. Elmqvist, L. Gunderson, C. S. Holling, and B. Walker. (2002). Resilience and sustainable development: Building adaptive capacity in a world of transformations. *Ambio* 31:437-440.
- Fundación Nueva Cultura del Agua (2005). *Declaración Europea por una Nueva Cultura del Agua*. Madrid: FNCA.
- Gleick, P. H. (2003). Global Freshwater Resources: Soft-path solutions for the 21st Century. *Science*,302:1524-1528.
- Gibbons, M., C. Limoges, H. Nowotny, Eds. (1994). *The New Production of Knowledge*. London: Sage Publications
- Hare, M. P., O. Barreteau, B. Beck, R. A. Letcher, E. Mostert, J. D. Tàbara, D. Ridder, V. Cogan and C. Pahl-Wostl. (2006). Methods for Stakeholder Participation in Water Management. In: C. Giupponi, J. J. Jakeman, D. Karssenberg and M. P. Hare. *Sustainable Management of Water Resources*. Northampton, Massachussets: Edward Elgar. Pp. 177-225.
- Intergovernmental Panel For Climate Change (2001). *Climate Change. Impacts, Adaptations and Vulnerability. Contribution to the Third Assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 641-693.
- Kasemir, B.; J. Jäger, C. Jaeger and M. T. Gardner (Eds). (2003). *Public Participation in Sustainability Science*. A Handbook. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 81-104.
- Kasemir, B., U. Dahinden, A. Gerger, R. Schüle, D. Tàbara, C. C. Jaeger (2000). Citizens' perspectives on Climate Change and Energy Use. *Global Environmental Change*. 10(3):169-184.
- Ledoux, L., S. Cornell, T. O'Riordan, R. Harvey and L. Banyard (2005). Towards sustainable flood and coastal management: identifying drivers of, and obstacles to managed realignment. *Land Use Policy*: 129-144.
- Muller, A. (2003). A flower in full blossom? Ecological economics at the crossroads between normal and post-normal science. *Ecological Economics*, 45:19-27

Nowotny, H., P. Scott, and M. Gibbons (2001). *Re-Thinking Science: Knowledge and the Public in an Age of Uncertainty*. London: Polity Press.

Olson, P. C. Folke. and F. Berkes. (2004). 'Adaptive Co-management for Building Resilience in Social-Ecological System.' *Environmental Management* 34:75-90.

Tàbara, D. and A. Ilhan. (2006). 'Culture as trigger for sustainability transition in the water policy domain. The MATISSE project and the case of the Ebro River Basin'. Paper presented at the *5th Iberian Congress on Water Management*. Portugal. December. Matisse working paper 10 (download available at www.matisse-project.net).

Tàbara, D. , B. Elmqvist, A. Ilhan, C. Madrid, L. Olson, M. Schilperoord, P. Valkering, P. Wallman, (2006). 'Participatory Modelling For Integrated Water System Sustainability. The World Cellular Model and The MATISSE Project. Paper to be presented at the *I International Conference on Sustainability Measuring and Modelling*. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Terrassa, November. Matisse working paper 9 (download available at www.matisse-project.net).

Tàbara, D., (2006). *A comprehensive analysis of methods and tools for Integrated Sustainability Assessment of water using common generic principles*. Deliverable D6.2. MATISSE EU-project

Tàbara, D. (1999). *Acció ambiental. Aprenentatge i participació vers la sostenibilitat*. (Environmental Action. Learning and participating towards sustainability). Balearic Islands. 7 edició. SCEA-SBEA.

Van der Brugge, J. Rotmans, D. Loorbach. (2005). The transition in Dutch water management. *Regional Environmental Change*, available at: http://www.drift.eur.nl/publications/misc/transition_dutch_watermngmt.pdf

Weaver, P.M., D. Tàbara, J. Rotmans, A. Haxeltine, J. Jager, (2005). Sustainability: a systemic synthesis from the perspective of Integrated Sustainability Assessment. Matisse project. Deliverable D1.1.

Weaver, P.M. and J. Rotmans (2006). Integrated Sustainability Assessment: what is it, why do it, and how?, *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*. Vol. 1, No.4

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